

The charter is the foundational document that describes the rationale, goals, plan of work, resources needed, terms and conditions, and outcomes of a Center for Digital Humanities at Princeton (hereafter CDH) project. Charters are written by core members of a project team in a series of planning meetings taking place over the course of a month. The planning process is intensive, collaborative, and requires substantial input from everyone on a team. Charters serve as formalized agreements among all team members on such crucial questions as scope, technical design, infrastructural needs, and success criteria.

This is a digital copy of a “living document” at a single point in time. Charters are amended as necessary throughout the project lifecycle to document major changes and note when the “Built by CDH” Software Warranty and “Built by CDH” Long Term Service Agreement take effect, and serve as part of the CDH project archive. Certain components of the Charter, such as the Roadmap, are intended to be updated more frequently as development progresses and priorities naturally shift. For more information, see the Charter amendment policy located in the Agreements section of this Charter.

CDH charters and their planning documents exist in several forms as we have refined them over the years and tailored them to the several types of projects we have supported. For more about CDH project management, including the charter process, visit:

<https://cdh.princeton.edu/research/project-management>.

Cite this document:

Budak, Nick, Marina Rustow, Rebecca Sutton Koeser, Gissoo Doroudian, Natalia Ermolaev, Stephanie Luescher, and Rachel Richman. *CDH Project Charter — Princeton Geniza Project 2020-21*. Center for Digital Humanities at Princeton. 2020.
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081714>

Geniza Charter

2020-2021 CDH Research Partnership

Overview

Related documents

- For a list of terms and definitions used in this document and throughout the project context, see [Terms and Definitions](#).
- For a list of common workflows used on this and other CDH sponsored projects, see [Workflows](#).
- Crucial decisions made during this project's grant period and their rationale will be recorded in a private Decision Log document.

Background

The Princeton Geniza Project (PGP) currently comprises roughly 28,000 entries on documentary texts from the Cairo Geniza, a cache of roughly 380,000 fragmentary texts that survived for centuries in a medieval Egyptian synagogue. Most of the texts date from ca. 950–1250. They are housed today in more than 60 libraries and private collections. The material is centered on Cairo and Egypt, but covers an astonishingly wide geographic remit, stretching from Spain to Sumatra, and attests to one of the most geographically mobile societies of the medieval world. The documents include letters, legal texts, lists, accounts, and state administrative texts. Historians regard the geniza as one of the most exciting and productive source-bases for premodern economic and social history.

Since the 1980s, Princeton has been at the forefront of research on geniza documents. The Princeton Geniza Lab (PGL) was founded in 1985 by Mark Cohen and Avrom Udovitch (Department of Near Eastern Studies, now both emeriti). The PGL serves as a home for research projects that aim to expand the corpus of Geniza documents and supporting materials available to Geniza researchers; the PGP is its primary project.

For its first thirty years, the PGP's goal was to digitize transcriptions of Geniza documents in their original languages (Arabic, Aramaic, Hebrew and Judaeo-Arabic) and make them word-searchable. By 2015, the database had grown to 4,250 transcriptions and was an indispensable tool for research monographs on trade, Jewish communal organization, women, the family, and slavery.

After Cohen and Udovitch retired, Eve Krakowski and Marina Rustow were hired in 2015 and took over the running of the PGP. Rustow and Krakowski shifted the emphasis from producing transcriptions, a slow and painstaking process of use only to specialists, to developing more robust metadata on the documents. The PGP's current aim is to describe all the documentary texts in the geniza, a projected total of 40,000 items, and to add transcriptions in batches, whether grouped by document type (e.g., marriage contracts, bills of sale for real estate, tax receipts), scribe, or other criteria.

At present, PGP digital data exists in multiple formats and locations: transcriptions, descriptive metadata, manuscript images, translations and unpublished notes and comments. De-siloing the data is a high priority. Descriptive metadata is edited in a shared Google Sheet; transcriptions are stored separately as XML, and modifying them requires multiple steps. The project's current website reflects this siloing in its search interface, which cannot execute complex queries across all project data simultaneously. Under this charter, PGP seeks to partner with CDH to reunite the project data and imagine a user interface that brings together document images, metadata, and transcriptions via a powerful site search.

Data

A high-level view of PGP documents and metadata, and the order through which metadata is formed and the documents are identified.

Outcomes

In scope

Outcomes in this section are the primary goals of the research partnership for this grant period.

- Migrate existing document metadata to a relational database
- Migrate existing transcriptions to IIIF-compliant annotations
- Create protocols to guide continuing work on describing documents
- Create workflows for transcribing documents and editing transcriptions
- Design a new web application that supports searching the entire PGP
- Develop a private “alpha” version of the new web application

Out of scope

Outcomes in this section are not slated to be worked on during this grant period, but will be kept in mind when designing and architecting the new PGP site, with plans to revisit later.

- Incorporation of S. D. Goitein’s index cards in new application
- Migration of existing translations into standardized format; incorporation of translations in the new application
- Tracking use of PGP data in scholarship
- Full, production-ready replacement for current PGP website

Significance

Scholarly

The Cairo Geniza is the most robust source-base we have for the history of Jews in a period in which the vast majority of Jews lived under Muslim rule; it is also an unparalleled source for the history of the Islamic empires under which they lived. A pervasive challenge of the research is the diversity and dispersion of materials. The geniza’s contents are now housed in more than sixty libraries and private collections. Specialists on four continents are contributing their research to the field and to the PGP. The social and economic networks the geniza covers cross the globe, from the Mediterranean basin to the Indian Ocean, and the material is in four main languages (Arabic, Hebrew, Aramaic and Ladino) and two alphabets (Hebrew and Arabic). The bars to entering the field are so high as to have deterred even intrepid students from entering it. For all these reasons, simplifying workflows and desiloing the data will itself serve an important purpose in streamlining the research process and making it more accessible to those encountering it for the first time. Accessibility will, in turn, expand the kind of questions being asked of the material—questions we can’t and shouldn’t try to anticipate.

Research on geniza documents has thus far focused on a relatively narrow range of questions: trade and commerce; Jewish community politics; communal boundaries and religious conversion; Jewish law; and women, gender and the family. These questions reflect the interests of those typically able to enter the field with minimal start-up time. By streamlining the site and improving its accessibility, we hope to attract researchers with an interest in premodern global history and in areas of geniza research with untapped

potential: the history of labor, including women's labor; Indian Ocean history; technology and material culture; state administration; rural-urban relations; and long-distance trade and commerce. All these are areas of global history in which geniza sources are unparalleled in their quantity, coherence and density.

We hope that the fruits of this research partnership will also serve as a template for other corpora of unique and fragmentary handwritten documentary texts, as distinct from codices, printed works and other multi-page texts that exist in multiple copies.

Technical

This project will advance the scholarly use of annotation for research with the [Web Annotation Data Model](#) and [IIIF extensions for annotation](#). There are numerous projects working on annotation and transcription, but no existing tools provide a user interface to the Web Annotation features required for this project (including provenance, authorship attribution, documenting annotation language, and history and authorship of edits). By migrating existing Princeton Geniza Project transcription data and linking it to IIIF images (where possible), and developing workflows and tools to support working with the data, we will provide an exemplary use of Web Annotation for research data and will contribute to the tools and infrastructure available for working with Web Annotation and IIIF.

Design

The rich data of this project offer an opportunity to explore a new way of thinking about search and browse, one that is more holistic, where data is presented as intimately interconnected and explicable only by reference to the whole. The holistic approach empowers researchers, particularly those new to the materials, to gain a clearer understanding of the relationships in the data, and form new research questions they didn't know were possible. Because of the way data is presented, where potential stories await to be discovered, this approach encourages inclusivity and can attract a wider range of users with various professional backgrounds and interests to meaningfully understand the data landscape of the project or even take part in more in-depth research.

We will explore new approaches for the display of transcription information and interaction with it. Our approach will focus on taking users through a contextual journey, showing information not only where but also *when* it is cognitively and intuitively appropriate, as needed by the user. This will be a significant shift from the primarily text-based scholarship of the field, and will leverage the interactivity of web technologies to move beyond the typical navigational constraints of the existing annotation tools.

Risks and dependencies

- Migrating existing transcriptions to IIF annotations will make use of PUL infrastructure and interfaces. At the time of chartering, PUL is actively working to establish this infrastructure, but work is still in the early stages.
- Transcription data is currently managed solely by Ben Johnston of the McGraw Center for Teaching and Learning. Migrating this data will require working closely with Johnston.
- Document metadata is concentrated in a single large Google Sheet, collaboratively edited by many parties. Care must be taken to continue recording newly described documents while the new database is being developed.
- Updating the existing PGP interfaces to be automatically updated from changes to the data in the new system will require collaboration with Ben Johnston.
- Data cleaning and analysis in collaboration with Data-Driven Social Science Initiative (DDSSI) and Lori Bougher will inform and benefit database design and data migrations.

Budget

[Project budget available on request.]

Roles and responsibilities

Co-PI: Research Lead

Marina Rustow

- Maintains and communicates overall vision for the project with Technical Lead
- Provides leadership on the research side of the project; oversees project's content aspects
- Communicates and resolves high-level project issues with Technical Lead
- Conducts acceptance testing if necessary to verify project features align with vision
- Attends regular project check-in meetings during development process
- Learns enough about project's technical components to discuss them publicly
- Supervises and maintains active communication with the Project Manager
- Notifies team in advance of any disruptions to work or unavailability
- Approves Project Manager's work on publicity, including project page on CDH site

Co-PI: Technical Lead

Rebecca Sutton Koeser

- Maintains and communicates overall vision for the project with Research Lead
- Communicates and resolves high-level project issues with Research Lead
- Provides technical leadership; oversees design and implementation of project's technical aspects
- Adjusts choices of software tools and approach in order to achieve project goals
- Supervises software release process, including updating documentation
- Learns enough about project's scholarly aspects to discuss them publicly
- Can make project development decisions if Research Lead is unavailable
- Advises Project Manager on design and modification of project workflows
- Advises Project Manager on creation and modification of project data protocols
- Contributes to development, documentation, automated testing, and code review of software for the project

Project Manager (PM)

Stephanie Luescher (*September 2020–January 2021*)

Rachel Richman (*February–September 2021*)

- Schedules CDH project check-in meetings
- Schedules meetings with CDH and project collaborators (DDSSI, others)
- Creates agendas for project meetings; assigns facilitator(s)
- Identifies meeting action items and creates tasks using PM software
- Maintains awareness of current dev/design team work during active development
- Maintains and, if necessary, creates workflows to help team achieve its goals

- Conducts acceptance testing of project features, escalating to Director if needed
- Oversees day-to-day work of project data team for tasks specific to CDH-Geniza partnership
- Manages project publicity, including project page on CDH website, escalating to Director if needed
- Facilitates project retrospectives with assistance from CDH Project Manager

Assistant Project Manager

Rachel Richman (*September 2020–January 2021*)

Stephanie Luescher (*February–September 2021*)

- Serves as backup to Project Manager for work that spills over allotted hours
- Keeps up with project decisions and progress
- Answers questions based on decisions made as primary Project Manager

User Experience (UX) Designer

Gissoo Doroudian

- Chooses appropriate design tools for the project
- Conducts design testing of project user interface (UI)
- Makes decisions regarding project user interaction flow, UI: layout, color, and typeface, and visual design incorporating team input at design meetings
- Initiates collaborative and iterative design for information architecture (IA) and UI
- Incorporates usability and accessibility principles in designs
- Conducts UX research and/or usability testing when crucial prior to making design decisions

Research Software Developer

Nick Budak

Kevin McElwee

- Develops and documents software for the project
- Writes automated tests for software for the project
- Assists Technical Lead in choosing software tools and approach to the project
- Reviews code contributions from other Developers
- Delivers software features for acceptance testing; writes testing notes/instructions
- Delivers UI components for design testing; writes testing notes/instructions
- Assists Technical Lead in consulting and advising project team on data questions, workflows and tools

CDH Project Manager

Nick Budak

- Coordinates development and design work with other CDH projects and priorities
- Serves as a resource and point of contact for Project Manager
- Arranges meeting note-taking and agendas with Project Manager
- Assists PM and SRA with design and implementation of project workflows
- Supplies periodic updates on project status and progress via PM tooling (e.g. Asana)
- Assists PM in facilitating project retrospectives

Senior Research Assistant (SRA)

Alan Elbaum (*MS, UC Berkeley; MD candidate, UC San Francisco*)

- Creates and maintains project data protocols with Research Lead and Project Manager, in consultation with Technical Lead, Research Software Developers, and UX Designer
- Maintains broad knowledge of scope and shape of project data via frequent interactions directly with the data

Research Partnership Advisor

Natalia Ermolaev

Meredith Martin

- Advises Development and Design Team on high-level project direction (i.e. charter review, amendment review)
- Communicates overall CDH strategic and research priorities to Research Lead

Project Management Mentor

Rebecca Munson

Natalia Ermolaev

- Trains and mentors Project Manager in essential project management skills and practices
- Helps troubleshoot project or team-related issues

Administration and Finance

Elizabeth Samios (*CDH Business Manager*)

- Administers project funds

Deena Abdel-Latif (*Geniza Lab Coordinator*)

- Manages project funds
- Tracks and reports project team hourly work
- May assist PM with scheduling meetings

Roadmap

The roadmap is a high-level, strategic overview of planned development and design work for this grant period. It focuses on take-aways and decisions rather than products and is intended to be modified as the project progresses. Near-term events will necessarily have more detail than longer-term ones, reflecting the inherent uncertainty of digital product development.

Prior to the end of each of the phases listed below, the Project Manager and CDH Project Manager will facilitate a retrospective meeting at which team members will share and reflect on progress and lessons learned. At this meeting, the team will collaboratively outline a short statement that encompasses the major take-aways from the retrospective. The Project Managers will assign team members as needed to fill in details in the retrospective summary statement.

Prior to starting development at the beginning of each of the phases below, the Technical Lead will propose and circulate a more detailed roadmap for the next phase, based on the retrospective and current project priorities. The updated roadmap will be circulated to the project team for discussion and must be agreed upon by Technical Lead and Research Lead.

Fall 2020 (september–november)

Transcription data modeling

- Develop mapping for Geniza TEI transcription data to web annotation data model; review and refine with project team and PUL
- Write and test script to convert TEI data to web annotation; experiment with and review available tools, including PUL staging annotation server and eScriptorium
- Test preliminary transcription workflows on PUL IIF annotation server
 - editing migrated transcriptions
 - adding transcriptions manually
 - document limitations and problems
- Connect with the project's advisory group and an initial group of representative users, and conduct [UX research](#) and [usability testing](#) with them to learn about the goals, needs, and workflows for viewing, editing, and adding new transcriptions.

Goals

- Develop preliminary transcript data model and migration script
- Identify functionality requirements for working with transcriptions as web annotation
- Decide how to handle TEI content related to materials not available via IIF

- Identify annotation design needs and propose ways for users to interact with annotations (view and edit existing, add new)

Search prototype

- Index data in Solr; work with spreadsheet metadata and transcription data (preferably in web annotation; TEI will be used as a fallback).
- Develop a minimal Python/Flask application with Solr search (similar in some ways to [PEMM Incipit Search Tool](#)); iteratively prototype and refine basic and some advanced search features; use a CSS framework if styles are needed.
- Prototype holistic search approach with project data
- Conduct UX research, and usability testing iteratively with representative users to learn about the goals, needs, and workflows for search and browse, and propose and revise designs based on what has been learned.

Goals

Learn about project data and search options to inform database design and site design.

- Developers: Gain working familiarity with project data; determine what existing search functionality (filters, stemming, stopwords, etc) are available for the languages included in the project data and identify any gaps that will require additional development work
- Designer: test holistic search approach with project data: [information architecture \(IA\)](#) phase. And have a working prototype for usability testing to further refine the proposed designs.
- Project team members: Try out new search options and provide feedback

Multilingual prototype

- Develop a minimal Django application with internationalization and translation functionality.
- Conduct secondary research on designing multilingual user interfaces.
- Conduct UX research to learn about goals and needs for a multilingual site.

Goals

Learn enough about internationalization to decide whether we want to build the site as multilingual from the start.

- Developers: Understand technical and practical aspects of making a multilingual site
- Project team members: learn how to provide and manage translations for a multilingual site

- Designer: Identify how a multilingual site would impact the site's [interaction design \(IxD\)](#) and [user interface \(UI\)](#)

New PGP site

- Propose information categories and document as sitemap diagrams: IA
- Propose navigation avenues between information categories and document as site flow diagrams: IA phase
- Determine what design tool(s) should be used for the project

Deliverables

- Preliminary migration script for TEI content
- Database design for the new project site
- Decision on multilingual approach
- Sitemap and site flow diagrams for public site
- Summarized findings from all UX research and usability testing sessions
- Decision on design tools that will be used throughout the course of the project

Winter 2020 (december–february)

Data migration

- Initial implementation of relational database design in Python/Django with basic admin interface
- Migrate existing project metadata from Google Sheets
- Data exports
 - Enable simple admin data exports (CSV) for project team members to work with data outside the database
 - Implement a CSV data export to replace Google Sheets data so that the current PGP site can be kept up to date with changes in the database

New PGP site

- Create a low-fidelity version of the site using the content of the sitemap and site flow diagrams: [wireframing](#) (defined under “UI”)
 - Create and propose information types and details on each page
 - Create consistent information hierarchies within pages (will affect the UI)
 - Identify page types (what is similar and different among pages)
- Begin to design the UI of each page type in scope
- Begin to design the UI for [user journeys](#) (defined under “UI”) in scope

- Develop preliminary public site functionality ([alpha](#)) for view and basic search of migrated data in tandem with database and admin site work.

Transcription data

- Preliminary work with PUL and other partners on transcription data

Deliverables

- New database with basic admin interface
- Google sheets data migrated to database
- Early Alpha site for internal use and usability testing
- UI mockups for each page type
- UI mockups for types of user journeys (defined under “UI” in the link)
- Summarized findings from all usability testing sessions

Spring 2021 (march–may)

Transcription

- Work with PUL and other partners on building out transcription solution
 - Prioritize functionality for working with migrated transcriptions and editing existing transcriptions
- Incorporate Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) and segmentation tools from other projects (potentially including eScriptorium), where applicable and useful
- Finalize migration script from TEI to IIIF annotations and migrate existing transcription and translation data
 - Implement a data export to replace the TEI transcription data in bitbucket so that the current PGP site can be kept up to date with transcription changes

New PGP site

- Continue to develop the frontend interface, as prioritized by the team:
 - Refine and expand public site search based on project team priorities and usability testing on prototypes
 - Refine database and admin interface based on project team feedback
 - Implement new image + transcription view
 - Start implementing UI and [visual design](#) based on specifications created by the UX Designer
- Revise and/or complete the UI design mockups
- Complete the visual design

Deliverables

- TEI transcription data migrated to IIIF annotation
- Annotation functionality to support viewing and editing transcription data
- Enhanced Alpha site with more functionality
- Documentation for new transcription & translation workflow
- Summarized findings from all UX research and usability testing sessions
- Write-up of design exploration and findings including the ideas and their values, why they were or were not built, how they fit or did not fit the users' and project's goals and needs, and why, where, and how they can be applied.

Agreements

Charter amendments

While the Roadmap section of this document is expected to change as the grant period progresses, the Roles and Responsibilities and Agreements sections represent mutually binding terms between the CDH and its research partners. Adjustments to either of these two sections require an amendment document describing the proposed changes to be submitted for review by the CDH Research Partnership Advisor. Amendments are subsequently signed by the Research Lead and CDH Research Partnership Advisor to incorporate them into the project's charter.

Wrap-up

At the conclusion of the grant, the Project Manager and the Technical Lead will collaborate on a short (less than 500 words) summary of work that was accomplished during the grant period. The summary should describe the goals reached and outcomes of the project, and explain major changes and discrepancies with planned work. Continuing projects will include this information in the charter overview section for the subsequent phase of the project.

Project pause

To ensure that all projects receive sufficient and equitable staff time, time-sensitive development and design queries and requests must be addressed within two weeks of initial (email) request. The Research Lead is responsible for communication with the CDH Development & Design team. If the Director does not respond to a task that has been indicated as time-sensitive by the CDH team within 2 weeks of initial request, further project development will be paused until the project can be reasonably integrated back into the CDH development schedule.

Rights, permissions, and attribution

Site content and data will both be licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY 4.0). If any of the datasets consist solely of factual data where authorship cannot be claimed, they will be licensed as CC0.

Any software developed by CDH that merits release will be licensed under Apache 2.0. The Technical Lead will fill out an invention disclosure form in order to gain approval from the Office of Technology Licensing in order to release the code. Before approval is granted, the code will be owned by the Trustees of Princeton University.

Credit

All team members will be credited on the project's website and CDH project page. The project's website will include a sponsorship statement (indicating the CDH as well as any other supporting groups, departments, agencies) and will include a citation statement indicating how the project assets should be cited. The site will also list and link to other projects that contributed data. All contributors will be included in citations for the project as a whole or individual assets, including datasets.

Labor

Academic labor inherently involves imbalances of power. In accordance with CDH values, team members commit to ensuring that all project labor for this grant year will be compensated and credited – particularly with respect to contributions by undergraduate students, graduate students, and other vulnerable groups. Issues with compensation should be forwarded to the CDH Business Manager.